

THIOSEMICARBAZONE SCHIFF BASES OBTAINED FROM THE BIOLOGICALLY POTENT HETEROCYCLICS: SYNTHESIS AND CHARACTERIZATION

Himabindu Mekala*¹, Mamatha Kasula, Rambabu Palabindela¹,
Prabhakar Myadaraveni¹, Ramu Guda¹

¹Department of Chemistry, Kakatiya University, Warangal-506009, India.

Article Received on 05 May 2026,
Article Revised on 25 May 2026,
Article Published on 01 June 2026,

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20441134>

*Corresponding Author

Himabindu Mekala

Department of Chemistry, Kakatiya
University, Warangal-506009,
(Telangana) India.

How to cite this Article: Himabindu Mekala*¹, Mamatha Kasula, Rambabu Palabindela¹, Prabhakar Myadaraveni¹, Ramu Guda¹. (2026). Thiosemicarbazone Schiff Bases Obtained From The Biologically Potent Heterocyclics: Synthesis And Characterization. World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences, 15(6), 388–399.

This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license

ABSTRACT

All the chemicals used for this thesis work were purchased from sigma- Aldrich, TCI and Alfa Easer, all the solvents procured from SD fine and Finar with AR Dry Grade have been used without further purification. IR spectra were obtained from a Perkin–Elmer BX II spectrophotometer by using KBr discs and were reported in cm^{-1} units. UV–visible spectra were recorded using a Shimadzu-2600 spectrophotometer. The ¹H, ¹³C NMR spectra were recorded with a Bruker 500 MHz Avenue Ultra shield photo spectrometer at 500 MHz, 125 MHz respectively, using TMS for ¹H and ¹³C NMR, as references.

KEYWORDS: TCI and Alfa Easer, Perkin–Elmer BX II spectrophotometer, ¹H, ¹³C NMR, TMS for ¹H and ¹³C NMR.

INTRODUCTION

The production of organic ligands with various donor groups that have biological importance is of increasing interest in coordination chemistry. Transition metals play an essential role in medicinal chemistry, in the complexation being used as medications for the treatment of a variety of disorders. Stable and non-toxic metal compounds with active metal centres are useful as probes for biological systems. The environment around the metal centre, such as coordination geometry, ligands, and their donor groups, are essential for metal proteins to perform specific physiological tasks. Schiff bases are a significant class of compounds with a distinctive C=N group. Hugo Schiff identified the

reaction between a carbonyl molecule and an amine that results in the creation of the Schiff base ligand in 1864. These are thought to be one of the most promising chelate classes for metallo-organic hybrid species. Schiff bases have a strong chelation affinity for transition metal ions. Schiff base transition metal complexes are among the most investigated coordination molecules due to their biochemical, analytical, and antibacterial properties. Platinum based metal complexes are widely used as novel anticancer drugs.

Thiosemicarbazides (TSC) are a type of scaffolds that can be found in a variety of biologically active compounds. Synthesis and characterisation of nitrogen and sulphur donor ligands has emerged as one of the most important topics of coordination chemistry in recent years. Because of their various binding mechanisms, structural variability, and prospective biological implications, thiosemicarbazides and associated metal complexes have gotten a lot of interest among nitrogen/sulfur compounds. Their coordination flexibility is attributed to a number of variables, like intramolecular hydrogen bonding, a bulkier coligand, azomethine carbon atom steric crowding, and p-p stacking interactions. Potential donor atoms with a range of coordination modes enable ligands to form transition metal mono or polynuclear complexes with the metal ion in a neutral or deprotonated state.

Metal complexes produced from ligands enclosed by N, O, and S donor atoms are particularly appealing because of the chelation stability they provide to their complexes. Metal derivatives of thiosemicarbazones and substituted thiosemicarbazones with appropriate metal ions have become a reliable source for the discovery of novel biologically active compounds.^[20,21] In addition to improving biological activity, metal derivatives of thiosemicarbazones and substituted thiosemicarbazones with appropriate metal ions often lead to reduced toxicity through synergistic effects and have become a reliable source for the discovery of novel biologically potent thiosemicarbazones as antibacterial, antifungal, anti-tumor, anti-cancer, and anti-inflammatory, compounds.^[22-25] Hence, we decided to synthesize complexes as putative antimicrobial medicines with this functionality that could deliver superior therapeutic effects because of the thiosemicarbazone moiety which looks to be a potential pharmacophore in several pharmacologically active drugs. In order to develop new metal-based therapies, detailed analyses of their molecular structure and coordination mechanisms are required. Indole is a benzopyrrole in which the benzene and pyrrole rings are fused at the pyrrole nucleus's 2- and 3- locations. Indole derivatives have picked up a huge number in organic synthesis's interest due to their wide range of biological actions, including

antibacterial, antiinflammatory, analgesic, anticonvulsant, antimalarial, anticancer, and antiulcer properties. 1HIndole-2,3-dione (isatin) and its derivatives have a wide range of biological capabilities, including antituberculosis, antiviral, and anticancer activities.^[26,28]

Chromones (1-benzopyran-4-one) are a category of naturally occurring chemicals that are found throughout the nature, particularly in the plant kingdom.^[29] They are benzo-annulated 4pyran ring heterocyclic compounds that generate oxygen. Recent research has focused on molecules with the chromone structure (such as flavonoids and chromones), primarily due to their biological and physiological activities, which include antimycobacterial, antifungal, anticonvulsant, antimicrobial, mushroom tyrosinase inhibition, intermediates with a variety of fine chemical products,^[30,31] and so on. Furthermore, chromone hydrazones and their metal complexes exhibit antimicrobial, anti-tuberculostatic, anti-cancer, anti-oxidant, and other biological and therapeutic functions^[32,34]

The literature indicates that there is a notable lack of work on the biological activity of Nbenzyl piperidine-4-one derivatives as an antimicrobial agent. In the light of these observations, and in continuation of our current research on the synthesis and biological evaluation of small bioactive molecules, we have decided to synthesize and their metal complexes characterize of anthracene, indole, piperadine and chromone condensed thiosemicarbazone ligands. These have been synthesized by reported methods with small modifications from thiosemicarbazone scaffolds and evaluated their biological potency by studying their antimicrobial and anticancer activities and their binding capabilities by studying their molecular docking studies against EGFR, HER2, and IKK- β target proteins.

Thiosemicarbazone derivatives: The scaffold used in the present study

MATERIALS & METHODS

All the chemicals used for this thesis work were purchased from sigma- Aldrich, TCI and Alfa Easer, all the solvents procured from SD fine and Finar with AR Dry Grade have been used without further purification. IR spectra were obtained from a Perkin-Elmer BX II spectrophotometer by using KBr discs and were reported in cm^{-1} units. UV-visible spectra

were recorded using a Shimadzu-2600 spectrophotometer. The ^1H , ^{13}C NMR spectra were recorded with a Bruker 500 MHz Avenue Ultra shield photo spectrometer at 500 MHz, 125 MHz respectively, using TMS for ^1H and ^{13}C NMR, as references.

Experimental Section

Scheme-1

All the above mentioned ligands have been synthesized by the well-established and reported methods.

1. Synthesis of anthracene thiosemicarbazone (ATSC) L1

Thiosemicarbazide (91 mg, 1 mmol) and 9-anthraldehyde (206 mg, 1 mmol) were mixed in 15 ml of ethanol with a few drops of glacial acetic acid to make anthracene thiosemicarbazide (ATSC). The mixture was cooled at room temperature after 4 hours of refluxing. The orangeyellow precipitate was obtained from filtration, which was then washed with cold ethanol and ether and vacuum-dried. It was recrystallized in ethanol.

Yield: 76%. ^1H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO) δ 11.70 (s, 1H), 9.34 (s, 1H), 8.69 (s, 1H), 8.588.56 (m, 2H), 8.55 (m, 1H), 8.12 (d, $J = 7.2$ Hz, 2H), 7.76 (s, 1H), 7.66-7.64 (m, 2H), 7.62-7.55 (m, 2H). ^{13}C NMR (126 MHz, DMSO) δ 178.49, 142.64, 131.32, 130.10, 129.91, 129.42, 127.78, 126.04, 125.45, 125.24. IR (KBr pellet, cm^{-1}): ν 3448, 3193, 3044 (NH₂, NH), 1640 (C=N), 908 (C=S). HRMS: m/z $[\text{M} + \text{H}]^+$ 280.321. Anal. Calcd for C₁₆H₁₃N₃S: C, 68.79; H, 4.69; N, 15.04. Found: C, 68.68; H, 4.8; N, 14.89.

2. Synthesis of indole thiosemicarbazone (ITSC)

Indole thiosemicarbazone (ITSC) was made by mixing Indole 3-carboxaldehyde (146 mg, 1 mmol) and thiosemicarbazide (91 mg, 1 mmol) in a 1:1 ratio in 20 ml of ethanol with a catalytic quantity of acetic acid. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 4 hours, monitored using TLC, and then cooled and filtered. After washing with Methanol and recrystallizing with a 1:2 ratio of DCM and Methanol, a white coloured precipitate was produced.

Yield: 72%. ^1H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO) δ 11.59 (s, 1H), 11.21 (s, 1H), 8.35 (d, $J = 1.9$ Hz, 1H), 8.25 (d, $J = 7.3$ Hz, 1H), 8.06 (s, 1H), 7.81 (d, $J = 2.6$ Hz, 1H), 7.44 (d, $J = 8.1$ Hz, 2H), 7.20 (s, 1H), 7.15 (d, $J = 7.0$ Hz, 1H). ^{13}C NMR (126 MHz, DMSO) δ 177.01, 141.38, 137.52, 131.43, 124.46, 123.16, 122.60, 121.15, 112.25, 111.62: FT-IR (KBr): ν , cm^{-1} 3449 (N-H), 3309, 3230 (H-N-C=S), 1610 (C=N), 836 (C=S). HRMS: m/z 219.063 (M+H)⁺; Anal. Calc. For C₁₀H₁₀N₄S (%): C, 55.03; H, 4.62; N, 25.67.; Found: C, 54.92; H, 4.53; N, 25.01. UV-Vis (CH₃OH): λ_{max} , 262, 329 nm.

3. Synthesis of piperidinone thiosemicarbazone (PTSC):

Piperidinone thiosemicarbazone was prepared by combining 4-benzylpiperidone (189 mg, 1 mmol) and thiosemicarbazide (91 mg, 1 mmol) in 15 ml of dry THF by adding 2 drops of acetic acid. The reaction mixture was heated to 80° C and then cooled for 12 hours. The

reaction mixture was cooled to room temperature and the solvent was removed by rota vapour to obtain the solid product. The obtained percentage of the product is 68%.

Yield: 68%. MP 138 °C: ^1H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO) δ 10.21 (s, 2H), 8.02 (s, 1H), 7.347.32 (m, 5H), 3.51 (s, 2H), 2.43 (t, $J = 5.5$ Hz, 4H), 2.32 (t, $J = 5.8$ Hz, 4H). ^{13}C NMR (126 MHz, DMSO) δ 179.05, 154.33, 138.77, 129.21, 128.68, 127.45, 61.70, 53.66, 52.33, 34.56, 27.75. FT-IR (KBr): ν , cm^{-1} 3386 (N–H), 3240, 3197 (H–N–C=S), 1643 (C=N), 807 (C=S). HRMS: m/z $[\text{M} + \text{H}]^+$ 263.1331. Anal. Calc. For $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_4\text{S}$ (%): C, 59.51; H, 6.92; N, 21.35; Found: C, 59.20; H, 6.32; N, 21.01.

4. Synthesis of chromone thiosemicarbazone (CTSC)

The Schiff base Chromone thiosemicarbazone (CTSC) was synthesized by reacting thiosemicarbazide (91 mg, 1 mmol) with 3-formylchromone (248 mg, 1 mmol) in 20 ml of ethanol with 2 drops of acetic acid, by refluxing the mixture for 8 hours. The obtained product was cooled and filtered. The product was recrystallized with DMF and methanol, which yields a in a yellow crystalline solid.

Yield: 79%. Mp: 245 °C. ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6 , δ ppm, J Hz): 11.48 (s, 1H, -NH-C=S), 9.09 (s, 1H, CH=N), 8.16 (s, 2H, NH₂), 8.04 (s, 1H), 8.15– 8.12 (dd, $J = 1.6, 8, 1\text{H}$), 7.78– 7.84 (m, 1H), 7.49–7.53 (m, 1H), 7.72–7.73 (d, ($J = 8$), 1H). ^{13}C NMR (126 MHz, DMSO) δ 177.32, 157.25, 157.12, 143.63, 132.82, 130.87, 129.43, 128.90, 128.23, 126.30, 122.56. IR (KBr disks, cm^{-1}): ν 3391, 3216, 3129 (NH), 1642 (C=O), 1540 (C=N), 841 (C=S), UV–Vis (DMSO). HRMS: m/z $[\text{M} + \text{H}]^+$ 248.0494. Anal. Calcd for $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_9\text{N}_3\text{O}_2\text{S}$: C, 53.43; H, 3.67; N, 16.99%.

Found: C, 53.30; H, 3.51; N, 16.67; S, 12.89%. λ_{max} (e): 282, 309 nm.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The synthesis of the proposed thiosemicarbazone derivatives (**L1-L4**) was carried out using a simple, green, and cost-effective process that included the reaction of thiosemicarbazide with various substituted carbonyl compounds. According to Scheme 1, a variety of thiosemicarbazones were synthesized.

All the synthesized compounds ATSC, ITSC, PTSC and CTSC were characterized by using spectroscopic techniques such as NMR (^1H , ^{13}C), FT-IR, UV-visible, HRMS, and elemental analysis. IR spectral data of these thiosemicarbazones are discussed here. The primary functional groups among the synthesized ligands are C=S, C=N, C=O, -NH, and -NH₂ groups.

For the ligand ATSC, the peak intensities at 3448 cm⁻¹ and at 3193 cm⁻¹ indicates the presence of -NH₂, -NH groups. The peaks at 1640 cm⁻¹ and at 908 cm⁻¹ are corresponding to C=N and C=S functional groups. In ligand ITSC, the peak intensities corresponding to -NH₂, and NH are observed at 3449 cm⁻¹ and at 3309 cm⁻¹ and the peaks at 1610 cm⁻¹ and at 836 cm⁻¹ indicates the functional groups C=N and C=S. In PTSC the peaks corresponding to -NH₂, and NH were obtained in the region of 3386 cm⁻¹, and at 3240 cm⁻¹ and the peaks corresponding to C=N and C=S are observed at 1542 cm⁻¹, and at 841 cm⁻¹ and for the ligand CTSC the peaks corresponding to -NH₂, NH and for C=N and for C=S were observed at 3386 cm⁻¹, 3240 cm⁻¹ and at 1643 cm⁻¹, at 807 cm⁻¹ respectively. The Avance Bruker 500 MHz spectrophotometer was used to record the ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectrum data. The single N-H proton of ATSC appeared at 11.70 ppm in ^1H NMR spectra, while the C-H proton of anthracene appeared at 9.34 ppm. Imine CH was found at 8.69 ppm, and NH₂ protons were found at 8.12 ppm. All of the other aromatic protons were determined to be in the range of 8.58-7.55 ppm. The compound ITSC had a ^1H NMR spectrum with the N-H proton at 11.59 ppm and the indole N-H proton at 11.21 ppm, and the imine CH proton at 8.35 ppm. All the aromatic protons were determined in the range of 8.25-7.20 ppm, while NH₂ protons were identified at 7.44 ppm. For the compound PTSC, the NH proton was found at 10.21 ppm, the NH₂ proton was discovered at 8.02 ppm, and the aromatic protons were observed in the range of 7.34 -7.32 ppm. For the compound CTSC, the NH proton was found at 11.48 ppm, the imine CH proton was found at 9.09 ppm, and the NH₂ protons were found at 8.16 ppm. Whereas all the aromatic protons were found to be in the range of 8.04 -7.73 ppm. C atom of C=S obtained at 178.49 ppm for ATSC, imine C atom obtained at 142.64 ppm, and all other carbon atoms obtained in the range of 131.32 ppm to 125.24 ppm in ^{13}C NMR Spectral data. The carbon of C=S appears at 177.01 ppm in the second compound ITSC, while the imine carbon appears at 141.01 ppm. In between the range of 137.52 ppm to 111.62 ppm, all the aromatic carbon atoms were appeared. The carbon of C=S of thiosemicarbazide was found at 179.05 ppm in the compound PTSC, while the imine carbon was found at 154.33 ppm, leaving all the aromatic carbons in the range of 138.77 ppm to 127.45 ppm. In the compound

CTSC, the carbon atom of C=S is represented by 177.32 ppm, the imine carbon atom is represented by 157.25 ppm, and the aromatic carbon atoms are distributed between 143.63 and 122.56 ppm. For all of the compounds' HR mass spectra were recorded, the mass spectral data revealed that, for ATSC's m/z is 280 $(M+H)^+$, for ITSC's m/z is 219 $(M+H)^+$, for PTSC's m/z is 263 $(M+H)^+$, and for CTSC's m/z is 248 $(M+H)^+$. Elemental analysis is also one of the characterization techniques. Where we can find the % of C, H, and N present in the compounds. The structures of all the produced compounds were validated by the above-mentioned characterization techniques.

CONCLUSION

The four thiosemicarbazide condensed ligands were synthesized with anthracene, indole, 4-piperidinone, and chromone carboxaldehydes. In this report, the synthesized thiosemicarbazones ATSC(L1), ITSC(L2), PTSC(L3), and CTSC(L4) were characterized by 1H , ^{13}C NMR, FT-IR, UV-vis, HRMS, and elemental analyses techniques which were used to completely describe the characteristic features of all the compounds. All the characteristic data obtained is supporting the structure of the compounds listed above.

1. SPECTRAL DATA OF THE SYNTHESIZED LIGANDS

a. Ligand ATSC (L1) (1H and ^{13}C NMR)

Ligand L2 (ITSC) (¹H and ¹³C NMR)

Ligand L3 (PTSC) (¹H and ¹³C NMR)

IR Spectral data of L1-L4

L1

L2

L3

REFERENCES

1. M.A. Ali, S.E. Livingston, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1974; 13: 101.
2. M.J.M. Campbell, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1975; 15: 279.
3. S. B. Padhye, G.B. Kauffman, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1985; 63: 127.
4. D.x. West, S.B. Padhye, P.B. Sonawane, *Struct. Bonding*, 1991; 76: 1.
5. D.X. West, A.E. Liberta, S.B. Padhye, R.C. Chitake, P.B. Sonawane, A.S. Kumbhar, R.G. Yerande, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1993; 123: 49.
6. J.S. Casas, M.S. Garcia - Tasende, J. Sordo, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 2000; 209: 197.
7. H.G. Petering, H.H. Buskirk, G.E. Underwood, *Cancer Res.*, 1964; 24: 367.
8. J.S. Casas, M.S. Garcia-Tasende, J. Sordo, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 2000; 209: 197.
9. P.P. Netalkar, S.P. Netalkar, V.K. Revankar, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 2014; 39: 519.
10. D. Mishra, S. Naskar, M.G.B. Drew, S.K. Chattopadhyay, *Inorg. Chim. Acta.*, 2006; 359: 585.

11. R. Prabhakaran, P. Kalaivani, S.V. Renukadevi, R. Huang, K. Senthilkumar, R. Karvembu, K.Natarajan, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2012; 51: 3525.
12. L. Ze-hua, D. Chung-Ying, L. Ji-hui, L. Young-jiang, M. Yu-hua, Y. X-Zeng, *New J Chem.*, 2000; 24: 1057.
13. F. Basuli, S.M. Peng, S. Bhattacharya, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1997; 36: 5645.
14. C. Metcalfe, J.A. Thomas, *Chem. Soc. Rev.*, 2003; 32: 215.
15. M. Poyraz, M. Sari, F. Demirci, M. Kosar, S. Demirayak, O. Buyukgungor, *Polyhedron*, 2008; 27: 2091.
16. L.S. Shebaldina, O.V. Kovalchukova, S.B. Strashnova, B.E. Zaitsev, T.M. Ivanova, *Russ. J. Coord. Chem.*, 2004; 30: 38.
17. R. Prabhakaran, K. Palaniappan, R. Huang, M. Sieger, W. Kaim, P. Viswanathamurthi, F. Dallemer, K. Natarajan, *Inorg. Chim. Acta.*, 2011; 376: 317.
18. H.B. Shawish, M. Paydar, C.Y. Looi, Y.L. Wong, E. Movahed, S.N.A. Halim, W.F. Wong, M. Mustafa, M.J. Maah, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 2014; 39: 81.
19. R. Prabhakaran, P. Kalaivani, P. Poornima, F. Dallemer, G. Paramaguru, V. Vijaya Padma, R. Renganathan, R. Huange, K. Natarajan, *Dalton Trans.*, 2012; 4: 9323.
20. Z. Iakovidou, E. Mioglou, D. Mourelatos, A. Kotsis, M.A. Demertzis, A. Papagoergiou, J.R. Miller, D. Kovala-Demertzi, *Anticancer Drugs*, 2001; 12: 65.
21. D. Kovala-Demertzi, M.A. Demertzis, J.R. Miller, C. Papadopoulou, C. Dodorou, G. Filousis, *J. Inorg. Biochem.*, 2001; 86: 555.
22. K.S. Abou melha, *J. Enzyme Inhib. Med. Chem.*, 2008; 23: 493.
23. A.E. Liberta, D.X. West, *BioMetals*, 1992; 5: 121.
24. Z. Afrasiabi, E. Sinn, S. Padhye, S. Dutta, S. Padhye, C. Newton, C.E. Anson, A.K. Powell, *J. Inorg. Biochem.*, 2003; 95: 306.
25. R. Katwal, H. Kaur, B.K. Kapur, *Sci. Rev. Chem. Commun.*, 2013; 3: 1.
26. N. Terzioğlu, N. Karalı, A. Gürsoy, C. Pannecouque, P. Leysen, J. Paeshuyse, J. Neyts, E. De Clercq., *Arkivoc.*, 2006; 1: 109.
27. D. Banerjee, P. Yogeewari, P. Bhat, A. Thomas, M. Srividya, *Eur. J. Med. Chem.*, 2011; 46: 106.
28. S.Y. Abbas, A.A. Farag, Y.A. Ammar, A.A. Atrees, A.F. Mohamed, A.A. El-Henawy, *Monatsh. Chem.*, 2013; 144: 1725.
29. V.Y. Sosnovskikh, *Russ. Chem. Rev.*, 2003; 72: 489.
30. G. Singh, R. Singh, N.K. Girdhar, M.P.S. Ishar, *Tetrahedron*, 2002; 58: 2471.

31. L.Z. Piao, H.R. Park, Y.K. Park, S.K. Lee, J.H. Park, M.K. Park, *Chem. Pharm. Bull.*, 2002; 50: 309.
32. B.K. Kaymakcioglu, S. Rollas, *Farmaco*, 2002; 57: 595.
33. S. Küçükgülzel, S. Rollas, I. Küçükgülzel, M. Kiraz, *Eur. J. Med. Chem.*, 1999; 34: 1093.
34. S.R. Zhang, A.D. Sherry, *J. Solid State Chem.*, 2003; 171: 38.